

Sulfur-bearing molecules in a sample of early star-forming cores

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1. Appendix F: Measured parameters from the molecular lines

Tables F.1. and F.2. present the line parameters, Peak, Δv and the integrated emission (W), obtained from each analyzed molecular line from Gaussian fittings. For an example of such fittings see Appendix G.

2. Appendix G: Example of spectra and Gaussian fittings

As an example, Figures G.1., G.2., and G.3. display the spectra of band 7, spectral windows (spw) 16, 18, and 22, respectively, extracted from a beam centered at the position of the main core embedded in the ATLASGAL clump 337.9154–0.4773. The sulfur-bearing molecules are identified. The molecular line identification was made using CASA software by cross checking with the JPL and CDMS databases using the Splatalogue¹. Gaussian fittings are also included. Additionally, also as an example, Fig. G.4. displays a band 7 spw 20 spectrum towards the same source showing the CH₃OH 7(1,7)–6(1, 6)++ and 12(1,11)–12(0,12)–+ lines used to obtain the core temperature. Gaussian fittings are also displayed.

¹ <https://splatalogue.online/#/advanced>

Fig. G.1.: ALMA band 7 spw16 spectrum obtained towards the core in the ATLASGAL source 337.9154–0.4773. The analyzed SO^+ $J=15/2-13/2$ and H_2CS $J=10-9$ lines are indicated with their Gaussian fittings (red and blue, respectively).

Fig. G.2.: ALMA band 7 spw18 spectrum obtained towards the core in the ATLASGAL source 337.9154–0.4773. The analyzed NS $J=15/2-13/2$ and $\text{SO } 3\Sigma$ $J=9-8$ lines are indicated with their Gaussian fittings (red and blue, respectively).

Fig. G.3.: ALMA band 7 spw22 spectrum obtained towards the core in the ATLASGAL source 337.9154–0.4773. The analyzed ^{34}SO $J=7-6$ and SO_2 $J=8-7$ lines are indicated with their Gaussian fittings (red and blue, respectively).

Fig. G.4.: ALMA band 7 spw20 spectrum obtained towards the core in the ATLASGAL source 337.9154–0.4773. The used CH_3OH 7(1,7)–6(1, 6)++ and 12(1,11)–12(0,12)–+ lines to obtain the core temperature are indicated with their Gaussian fittings (red and blue, respectively).